

PREVENTION OF NURSE-MENTAL STRESS IN FUTURE GENERAL PRACTICE DOCTORS

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Introduction. Today, the socio-psychological components of the professional activity of general practitioners and its stress potential remain without due attention from researchers. Specialists from various fields are trying to fill the very concept of a general practitioner with meaning and, on this basis, determine its main functions and problematic aspects. However, as practice shows, there is a lack of a unified approach to this problem [1,2,3,4,6]

Purpose of the study: To determine the dynamics of the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress among future general practitioners before and after the training program.

Material and methods of research: For the purpose of the study, the dynamics of the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress among future general practitioners was identified, an empirical study was organized and conducted, in which 98 future general practitioners, third, fourth and fifth years of study, both female and female, took part. and also male. To achieve the goal, a questionnaire was used to determine neuropsychic stress by T.A. Nemchina[5].

Result and discussion. The analysis of the results of the first and second psychodiagnostic examinations showed that, following the results of the training program, future general practitioners of the experimental group (n=98) significantly improved the severity of the previously identified complex of individual psychological characteristics interpreted as a group of personal determinants of professional stress. Thus, the number of respondents with a high level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress (diagnosed using the Questionnaire for Determining Neuropsychic Tension by T.A. Nemchin) decreased from 50% (49 people - before the training program) to 8.2% (8 people - after the training program). Accordingly, future general practitioners with average and low levels of neuropsychic stress increased from 50% (49 people - before the training program) to 91.8% (90 people - after the training program).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the level of severity of neuropsychic stress in the experimental group of future practitioners before and after training sessions (n=98)

Conclusion: As a result, the level of manifestation of neuropsychic stress among future general practitioners decreased.

References:

- 1.Абабков В.А., Перре М. Адаптация к стрессу. Основы теории, диагностики, терапии. - Спб.: Речь, 2004. - 166 с.
- 2.Баймуратов Т.Р., Еникеева А.М., Кутдусова Э.Д., Насретдинова Л.М., Хусаенова А.А. Особенности общения медработников и пациентов, перенёвших инсульт // Молодой ученый. - 2019. - №7. - С. 129-131.
- 3.Водопьянов У.В. Стресс в современных условиях. - М.: Наука, 2010. - 140 с.
- 4.Кузнецов А.С. Признаки стресса в поведении человека // Молодой ученый. - 2019. - №51. - С. 462-464.
- 5.Немчин Т.А. Состояния нервно-психического напряжения / Т.А. Немчин. - Ленинград: Издательство Ленинградского университета, 1983. - 167 с.
- 6.Kozybai N. Analysis of job stress levels and coping strategies in construction organization managers / N. Kozybai // Тези Міжнародної конференції з економічної психології "A boat trip through economic change": Proceedings of the IAREP/SABE/ ICABEEP 2010 Conference Cologne (September, Cologne). - 2010. - Vol. 29. - P. 307-308.

7. Норботаев Ф.М., Шухратовна А.Ф. ПРОЦЕСС ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ВО ВРЕМЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА // Журнал инноваций, реформ и развития «Спектр». – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 9-17.
8. Макситдин о'гли Н.Ф., Шухратова А.Ф. ГРУППИРОВКА ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПО СТЕПЕНИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПСИХИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ЧЕЛОВЕКА // Научный репозиторий. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 292-299.
9. Муратова Ш. Место психологической среды в семье по повышению активности студента в образовательном процессе // Кронос: психология и педагогика. – 2019. – №. 3 (20). – С. 29-31.
10. Разыкова Л. Т. Игамова Ионят Сулеймановна, Рахматова Фатима Ганиевна, Муратова Шоиста Норбоваевна, Мамадиярова Дилфуза Умрзаковна, Кучкарова Ойша Олтибаевна Эффективность педагогического общения в подготовке врачей // Наука и образование сегодня. – 2019. – Т. 11. – С. 46.
11. Alisherovna A. G. et al. TIBBIYOT SOHASIDA IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK BILIMLARNI O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI // International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2024. – Т. 12. – №. 5. – С. 498-502.
12. Alisherovna A. G. PSIXOLOGIYADA SHAXS MUAMMOSI. SHAXSNING PSIXOLOGIK ASPEKTLARI // International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2024. – Т. 12. – №. 5. – С. 492-497.
13. Alisherovna A. G. et al. THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE IN THE FIELD OF MEDICINE // Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research Fundamentals. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 03. – С. 23-26.
14. Ўғил болаларни оилавий ҳаётга тайёрлашнинг ижтимоий-психологик жиҳатлари. СамДУ илмий ахборотнома. ISSN: 2091-54-46, 2020, 6-сон (124), - Б. 100-105. [19.00.00 №10]
15. Муратова Ш.Н. Никоҳ олди омилларининг йигитларни оилавий ҳаётга тайёрлашдаги ижтимоий-психологик имкониятлари. БухДУ психоло-гия илмий журнал. ISSN 2181-5291, 2021, 3-сон, - Б. 84-90. [19.00.00 №10]